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CHULPON AND HIS “NIGHT AND DAY”.

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Abstract

Key words: *Chulpon, Night and Day, novel, poem, Uzbek poet, jaded, Central Asia.*

Abdulhamid Sulaymon o‘g‘li Chulpon (1897 – 1938) is best known as the almost outstanding Uzbek poet of the twentieth century. When he emerged on the literary scene in the years following the Russian February Revolution of 1917, he became a leading voice for the new Turkic lyric that came to dominate Uzbek poetry in the 1920s. He developed a reputation for an elegiac style punctuated with colorful imagery and an innovative use of traditional symbols and metaphors. In the late 1920s, as Bolshevik – trained Uzbek intellectuals took over the literary sphere in Uzbekistan, Chulpon’s poetic fame transformed into notoriety. He became a political pariah, the subject of constant attacks in the press. In 1934, attempting to reconcile with Soviet power, he submitted the present novel, the first book of a planned trilogy *Night and Day*, to a Soviet literary contest. Three years later, Chulpon was arrested by the NKVD (the People’s Commissariat for Internal Affairs – Stalin’s secret police) as part of Stalin’s Great Terror (1936-1938). The work translated here, *Night*, was pulled from the shelves and banned; the sequel, if it existed, was likely destroyed by the NKVD. *Night* circulated in Uzbekistan in secret, influencing new generations of Uzbek litterateurs. Only with glasnost was the novel republished. It now stands as an exceptional piece of Uzbek prose. In the minds of Uzbek readers, *Night* tends to be overshadowed in the canon by the first Uzbek novel, Abdulla Qodiriy’s “*Bygone Days*” (*O‘tkan kunlar*, 1922), but Chulpon’s oeuvre is arguably the superior work.

In post – Soviet Uzbekistan, Chulpon is perhaps equally well-known as a so – called “national caretaker” (millatparvar). In the second decade of the twentieth

century, Chulpon and like-minded reformers, often called jadids, embraced a reformist discourse that involved, among other dimensions, an interest in European technology and the idea of the nation alongside traditional Islamic critiques of societal decline. The jadids implored their fellow urban Turkestanis to awaken themselves to the dangers of Russian colonialism and restore the lost glory of their people. Despite what modern Uzbek critics and Cold War-era Western researchers assert, these reformers' main rhetorical and political opponent was not Russian imperialists but the religious elite, the ulama, whom the jadids felt impeded their nation's progress towards modernity. For jadids, the Russian conquest of Turkestan was a result but not the cause of the decline of Islamic civilization. At the end of the present volume as Chulpon's character Razzoq-sufi, so names for his duty to perform the call to prayer, loses his grip on reality, the voices around him poignantly ask, "who is crazy? Th Russians or us?" These rhetorical questions direct the reader to first seek fault for the novel's tragedies in Turkestani backwardness. Naturally, educated reformers like Chulpon presented themselves as the people best suited to lead Central Asia in the twentieth century, a strategy which brought them into direct competition with the ulama for the ears of ordinary people. Russian colonial administrators, for their part, bridled jaded ambitions, consistently siding with the ulama in all disputes to maintain their rule over Central Asian society.

When the February Revolution came, Chulpon and his fellow jadids were quick to embrace it. Muslims reformers saw in the revolution a chance to increase Turkistan's autonomy within a new federation containing the territories of the former Russian Empire that would devolve power to the regions and champion democracy. Post-Soviet Uzbek historiography emphasizes that Chulpon and other jadids' eventual goal was independence, not simply autonomy, but this interpretation ignores jadids' precarious position in their own society. Jadids did not advocate independence because if Turkestan seprated from the Russianstate, they feared they would be left to the mercy of the ulama, who enjoyed more popularity among the masses than jadids. Because of jadids' socially marginl position and their understanding of history as expressed in their literature, Chulpon and his compratroits' literary works at this time portrary the February Revolution as something of a deus ex machine: it appeared as a sudden and unpricipitated solution to their problems. In a country moving to the left, suddenly the jadids were on the right side of history.

Chulpon's first published poem celebrated the February Revolution and socialist movements for these very reasons, seeing revolution as salvation from without. Published in 1918 but written in April of 1917, this excerpt from "Red Banner" demonstrates the poet's interest in the democratic and anti-imperial politics promised by socialism. It is important to remember that the poem by no means signals support

for the Bolsheviks, who were one among many socialist parties at the time. I have translated the bellow excerpt in a fashion that somewhat captures the caesura-inflected dtyle of the original. The original contains fifteen syllables per line and is read with slight pauses every four syllables(4-4-4-3). The rhyme scheme, which I have not captured here, is abab.

Red banner!

There, look how it waves in the wind,

As if the qibla(direction that Muslim should face when praying) wind is greeting it!

It is not glad to see the poor in this state,

For the poor man has the right because it is his.

Has the red blood of the poor not flown like rivers

To take the banner from the darkness into the light?

Are there no workers left in Siberian exile

To take the banner to the oppressed and weak people?

You , bourgeoisie, conceited upper classes, don't approach the red banner!

Were you not its bloodsucking enemy?

Now the black will not approach those white rays of light,

Now those black forces' time has passed!

As is typical of jaded literature at this time, Chulpon underplays Central Asian agency in the toppling of the Russian Empire by showing the February Revolution here as an event to which Central Asians have contributed little. As the first stanza indicates, Chulpon describes the revolution, the red banner of socialism, as the active observer of a passive Muslim East.

It is unclear when exactly Chulpon began writing his *Night and Day* but scholars speculate that he started around 1932 during his time in Moscow. As mentioned above, he submitted the first part of *Night and Day* to a contest for Uzbek socialist prose works towards the end of 1934. The judge, who wrote the report on the novel (Oydin, a major Soviet Uzbek poetess), noted that it lacked the proper ideological qualities necessary to be awarded a prize and expressed doubt that the proposed sequel, the content of which she seems to have known somewhat, would fix political mistakes. Nevertheless, the judges collectively recommended the novel for publication. The first chapter of the novel was published in the journal *Soviet Literature* (*Sovet Adabiyoti*) in the third issue of 1935, the second chapter was published in the tenth issue of *Rose Garden* (*Guliston*) in the same year, and the entire novel was published in October 1936 as a book. It received a short laudatory review in *Young Leninist* (*Yosh Leninchi*) in February of the following year, while all the other major critics held their tongues. Few dared to associate themselves with Chulpon publicly because of his reputation in the

press. Only in August of 1937, three critics coauthored a scathing review after Chulpon's arrest, targeting the writer for "replacing class struggle with pornography (parnografiya)", and "showing jadids as revolutionaries for the people" rather than as "allies of the Russian bourgeoisie and imperial officers. The book was banned along with the author's name.

Scientific resources.

1. Khalid, Making Uzbekistan: Nation, Empire, and Revolution in the Early USSR, 17
2. Abdulhamid Sulaymon o'g'li Cho'lpon, Asarlar: To'rt jildlik, vol. 1 (Toshkent: Akademnashr, 2016), 331.
3. Naim Karimov, Cho'lpon: Ma'rifiy roman (Toshkent: Sharq, 2003), 63
4. Brower, Turkestan and the Fate of the Russian Empire, 69
5. Richard A. Pierce, Russian Central Asia, 867- 1917: A Study in Colonial Rule (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1960), 216.